

《科学计量学导论》配套资料

参考文献：李杰，科学计量学导论[M]. 北京：首都经济贸易大学出版社. 2025.

科学计量学简史 (下册)

A Brief History of Scientometrics (Part II)

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版本：20240726

本资料为《科学计量学导论》（第一章）配套学习资料

1873

1873 : 弗兰克·谢泼德 (Frank Shepard, 1848–1900) 发布了《谢泼德索引》

(Shepard's Citator)。科学计量学的先驱加菲尔德 (Garfield) 明确承认, 《科学引文索引》

(Science Citation Index) 的想法源自谢泼德司法引证索引 (Garfield, 1955)。

GARFIELD E, 1955. Citation indexes for science: A new dimension in documentation through association of ideas[J]. Science, 122(3159):108-111.

1873

1873: 法国-瑞士植物学家阿尔丰沙·德堪多（Alphonse Pyramus de Candolle, 1806-1893）出版了《两百年来科学和科学家的历史》（de Candolle, 1873）。

Alphonse Louis Pierre Pyramus (or Pyrame) de Candolle (28 October 1806 – 4 April 1893) was a French-Swiss botanist, the son of the Swiss botanist Augustin Pyramus de Candolle.

de CANDOLLE A, 1873. Histoire des sciences et des savants depuis deux siècles: suivie d'autres études sur des sujets scientifiques en particulier sur la sélection dans l'espèce humaine.

1874

1874: 弗朗西斯·高尔顿爵士 (Sir Francis Galton, 1822-1911) 发表了《英国科学家：他们的天性和培养》 (Galton, 1874)。

Sir Francis Galton FRS FRAI (/ˈɡɔːltən/; 16 February 1822 – 17 January 1911) was an English polymath and the originator of the behavioral genetics movement during the Victorian era.

GALTON F, 1874. English Men of Science: Their Nature and Nurture[M]. London : Macmillan.

1895

1895：维尔弗雷多·帕累托（Vilfredo Pareto, 1848-1923）基于收入分配发现了首个幂律分布（Pareto, 1895）。

Vilfredo Federico Damaso Pareto (15 July 1848 – 19 August 1923) was an Italian polymath, whose areas of interest included sociology, civil engineering, economics, political science, and philosophy. He made several important contributions to economics, particularly in the study of income distribution and in the analysis of individuals' choices. He was also responsible for popularising the use of the term "elite" in social analysis.

PARETO V, 1895. La legge della domanda[J]. Giornale degli economisti, 59-68.

1906

1906: 美国心理学家詹姆斯·麦卡恩·卡特尔（James McKeen Cattell, 1860-1944）发表了《美国男性科学家名人录》（Cattell, 1906 a,b,c）。

James McKeen Cattell (May 25, 1860 – January 20, 1944) was the first professor of psychology in the United States, teaching at the University of Pennsylvania in Philadelphia. He was a long-time editor and publisher of scientific journals and publications, including *Science*, and served on the board of trustees for Science Service, now known as Society for Science from 1921 to 1944.

CATTELL JM, 1906a. A statistical study of American men of science: The selection of a group of one thousand scientific men[J]. *Science*, 24(621) :658-665.

CATTELL JM, 1906b. A statistical study of american men of science. II. The measurement of scientific merit[J]. *Science*, 24(622) :699-707.

CATTELL JM, 1906c. A statistical study of American men of science. III. The distribution of American men of science[J]. *Science*, 24(623) :732-742.

1913

Figure 1: Population and Absolute Concentration

1913: 德国物理学家费利克斯·奥尔巴赫（Felix Auerbach，1856-1933）发现了德国城市的等级和规模之间的双曲线关系（现在称之为齐普夫定律）（Auerbach, 1913）。

Felix Auerbach (12 November 1856 – 26 February 1933) was a German physicist.

AUERBACH F, 1913. Das Gesetz der Bevölkerungskonzentration[J]. Petermanns Geographische Mitteilungen, 59:74-76.

1916

1916: 法国速记员和速记作家让-巴蒂斯特·艾思杜（Jean-Baptiste Estoup, 1868-1950）发现词语的使用分布满足双曲函数性质，即齐普夫分布 (Estoup, 1916)。

Jean-Baptiste Estoup (16 January 1868, in Navenne – 17 April 1950, in Paris) was a French stenographer and writer on stenography. Estoup was General Secretary of the Institut Sténographique de France. In his *Gammes sténographiques* (3d ed. 1912), he pioneered the investigation of the regularity later known as Zipf's law.

ESTOUP JB, 1916. *Gamma Sténographique* (4th. ed.)[M]. Institut Sténographique de France, Paris.

1917

1917：科尔（F.J. Cole）和奈莉·伊尔斯（Nellie B. Eales）发表了《比较解剖学的历史》的典型科学计量学论文，其中包含了出版物数量等图形表示（Cole et al., 1917）。

Francis Joseph Cole FRS (3 February 1872 – 27 January 1959) was an English zoologist and a professor at the University of Reading for 33 years.

COLE FJ, EALES NB, 1917. The history of comparative anatomy: Part I.—A statistical analysis of the literature[J]. Science Progress (1916-1919), 11(44) :578-596.

<https://collections.reading.ac.uk/special-collections/collections/francis-cole-library-and-papers/>

1922

E. Wyndham Hulme (1859–1954)

1922: 温德姆·赫尔姆（Wyndham Hulme）引入了“书目统计（statistical bibliography）”这一术语。这些讲座内容在一年后正式出版（Hulme, 1923）。

HULME EW, 1922. University of Bristol Library National Liberal Club Collection. Statistical bibliography in relation to the growth of modern civilization : two lectures delivered in the university of cambridge in may 1922. Printed for the author by Butler & Tanner.

1925

Ryc. 1. Prof. dr hab. Stefan Zamecki (1937–2022) (źródło: p. M. Sobieszcza-Marciniak, córka Profesora)

1925: 科学史学家斯特凡·扎梅茨基（Stefan Zamecki）发表论文“Przedmiot i zadania nauki o wiedzy [The subject and tasks of the science of knowledge]”首倡创建一门叫做“科学学（波兰文:naukoznawstwo）”的学科（Zamecki et al., 2006）。

Stefan Zamecki（1936–2022年）自1975年起在波兰科学院科学、教育和技术历史研究所（1994年更名为波兰科学院科学史研究所）从事科学研究、科学哲学与历史、化学历史等领域的研究。他还在1999年至2018年期间担任《科学与技术历史季刊》的主编。

ZAMECKI S, ZNANIECKI F, 2006. Na marginesie rozprawy Znaniecki, Florian. Przedmiot i zadania nauki o wiedzy. Nauka Polska. Jej Potrzeby, Organizacja i Rozwój, 1925 tom V. Kwartalnik Historii Nauki i Techniki, 51(2):211-240.

1926

Alfred James Lotka (March 2, 1880 – December 5, 1949) was a Polish-American mathematician, physical chemist, and statistician, famous for his work in population dynamics and energetics.

1926: 阿尔弗雷德·詹姆斯·洛特卡 (Alfred James Lotka, 1880-1949) 撰写了《科学生产力的频率分布》，在该文中他发现了著名的洛特卡定律 (Lotka, 1926)。

LOTKA AJ, 1926. The frequency distribution of scientific productivity[J]. Journal of the Washington academy of sciences, 16(12):317-323.

plant pathology which he helped to elevate to a profession of high standing will endure for all time. In this line of endeavor nature's obedient response to his interrogations is well evidenced by a survey of the astonishing number of publications he has contributed, 167 original and 73 reviews, a total of 240.

It is not necessary to say to the friends of Dr. Smith that his culture was far more than plant pathological. An inherent love of the more refined embellishments of our civilization, especially literature, served to further distinguish this many-sided man. A patron of all the arts, he was a master of lucid composition and a gifted poet. A book of verse published privately in 1915, containing 197 sonnets and other original poems, together with understanding and sympathetic Latin translations from the German, French and Italian languages, is an achievement of his creative ability, practically unknown except to the small circle of friends among whom the limited edition was circulated. His fondness for the beautiful city of his adoption was not confined to a detached admiration of its charm. As a member of the Arts Club of Washington he actively served with the enthusiastic and disinterested groups of public-spirited citizens in movements designed for preserving its natural beauty and enhancing it with architectural adornments in keeping with the vision of L'Enfant.

A glimpse into his home disclosed a veritable treasure house of art objects and a superlative library selected with discriminating taste during a long lifetime of profound meditation on the serious things of this life and the hereafter. Dr. Smith was not a churchman in the sense of regular display of piety, but he was deeply religious and his faith as revealed in his written records constitutes an answer to the challenge of the fundamentalists who see in the interpretations of science an undermining of the structure of Christianity.

At a time when he could look back over the course of a long life rich in service to his fellowmen and just following the spontaneous tribute to his genius by his fellow scientists at the Philadelphia meetings of the American Association for the Advancement of Science he passed into the state which can not be voiced more fittingly than in his own words:

QUIETUDE: A PRAYER

God of all flesh, when these my days are sped
Let me but hear the music of the spheres
Or see, far off, the progress of the years
And I shall be greatwhile content though dead;
For to their heavenly music I am wed
And thrill with subtle thrills, nor yield to fears.
Thy great To-morrow wipes away all tears
And there, as here, Thy law shall be our bread.
Then let me dwell in some great quiet place

Where I may brood in peace on time's deep things
And all the mystery that round man clings;
Far off, mayhap, have glimpse of one sweet face;
And catch the tones of twanging golden strings
Whereto Thy myriad million stars keep pace!

E. W. BRANDES

UNITED STATES DEPARTMENT
OF AGRICULTURE

COLLEGE LIBRARIES AND CHEMICAL
EDUCATION

WHETHER we would have it or no, the purpose of the small college is changing. A decade ago the graduate of a college was thought to be fitted with the requisites of a cultural, liberal education, to be ready to begin his life work as a good citizen. Within a generation, however, has come an era of specialization. Everywhere we see the demand for the expert worker, the professional man who has devoted from two to four additional years to train himself in a special way in a particular field.

The small college has stood staunch in its desire to supply the liberal education and perhaps it has done well in maintaining this position. On the other hand, many of the large universities have shifted the emphasis from undergraduate work to graduate study. Still others have tried to develop both side by side. Few of the small colleges have kept astride with the inevitable consequences of such a situation. The few who have are sending an increasing number of their graduates to these universities to complete their training. As an example of this, it is the boast of Pomona College that over seventy per cent. of her graduates have taken subsequent professional training. It has become the evident duty, therefore, of the small college to prepare its men, not only to enter such graduate schools, but also to meet successfully the ever-increasing intensity of competition found there. This in addition to supplying a broad cultural education. This duty has brought with it a number of problems of first magnitude. One of the biggest of these is the problem of adequate library facilities.

It is the purpose of this paper to discuss this problem with special reference to the student whose college major is chemistry. The answer to the question of what books a library in chemistry should contain will be found excellently answered in a book, containing a list of 1,600 books, each one judged by experts as to importance and value. This book, edited by Patterson and Crane, will soon be available. The problem of the purchase of new books as they appear is one which must be answered anew for each

1927: P. L. K. 格罗斯和E. M. 格罗斯 (Gross et al., 1927) 出版了首篇使用引文分析的文章《大学图书馆与化学教育》(College Libraries and Chemical Education)。

1928

1928: 美国核物理学家、量子力学先驱贝尔实验室的爱德华·贡东 (Edward Uhler Condon, 1902-1974) 在Science发表了短文《词汇的统计》 (Statistics of vocabulary), 发现了词频和词序之间的双曲线性质 (Condon, 1928; Morse, 1976)。

Edward Uhler Condon (March 2, 1902 – March 26, 1974) was an American nuclear physicist, a pioneer in quantum mechanics, and a participant during World War II in the development of radar and, very briefly, of nuclear weapons as part of the Manhattan Project. The Franck–Condon principle and the Slater–Condon rules are co-named after him.

CONDON EU, 1928. Statistics of vocabulary[J]. Science, 67(1733) :300-300.

1929

George Kingsley Zipf (January 7, 1902 – September 25, 1950), was an American linguist and philologist who studied statistical occurrences in different languages.

1929: 乔治·金斯利·齐普夫 (George Kingsley Zipf, 1902-1950) 发表了其博士论文《相对频率作为语音变化的决定因素》 (Zipf, 1929)。

ZIPF GK, 1929. Relative frequency as a determinant of phonetic change[J]. Harvard studies in classical philology, 40:1-95.

1931

盖森（орис Михайлович
Гёссен，1893-1936）

1931：苏联代表团在在在英国伦敦南肯辛顿科学博物馆参加了1931年6月29日至7月3日的第二届国际科学技术史大会，并做了系列演讲。会后，形成了《十字路口的科学》论文集。其中，收录了盖森的《牛顿力学的社会经济根源》，对西方的科学学以及后来的科学计量学研究产生了深刻印象。

1932

George Kingsley Zipf (January 7, 1902 – September 25, 1950), was an American linguist and philologist who studied statistical occurrences in different languages.

1932: 乔治·金斯利·齐普夫 (George Kingsley Zipf, 1902-1950) 出版了《语言中相对频率的原则研究》，该书包括了对汉语词汇的规模-频率研究(Zipf, 1932).

ZIPF GK, 1932. Selected Studies of the Principle of Relative Frequency in Language[M]. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.

1934

1934：萨缪尔·克莱门特·布拉德福（Samuel Clement Bradford, 1878-1948）发表了《专门学科的情报源》（Sources of information on specific subjects），讨论了某一学科/主题下文献的分散性，后来这一理论被称为布拉德福定律（Bradford, 1934）。

Samuel Clement Bradford (10 January 1878 in London – 13 November 1948) was a British mathematician, librarian and documentalist at the Science Museum in London. He developed "Bradford's law" (or the "law of scattering") regarding differences in demand for scientific journals

BRADFORD SC, 1934. Sources of information on specific subjects[J]. Engineering, 137: 85-86.

1934

1934: 保罗·奥特莱（Paul Marie Ghislain Otlet, 1868-1944）首次提出了“bibliométrie（文献计量学）”（Otlet, 1934）。

Paul Marie Ghislain Otlet (23 August 1868 – 10 December 1944) was a Belgian author, entrepreneur, lawyer and peace activist; predicting the arrival of the internet before World War II, he is among those considered to be the father of information science, a field he called "documentation".

OTLET P, 1934. *Traité de Documentation. Le Livre sur le Livre. Théorie et Pratique*[M], Brussels: Van Keerberghen.

1935

1935: 波兰社会学家Maria Ossowska (1896-1974) 和Stanisław Ossowski (1897-1963) 发表了“科学的科学 (Nauka o nauce)”一文 (Ossowska et al., 1935; Ossowska et al., 1964)。

Maria Ossowska (née Maria Niedźwiecka, 16 January 1896, Warsaw – 13 August 1974, Warsaw) was a Polish sociologist and social philosopher.

Stanisław Ossowski (22 May 1897 – 7 November 1963) was a Polish sociologist. He held professorships at University of Łódź (1945–1947) and University of Warsaw (1947–1963).

OSSOWSKA M, OSSOWSKI S, 1935. Nauka o nauce[J]. Nauka Polska, 20(3):1-12.
OSSOWSKA M, OSSOWSKI S, 1964. The science of science[J]. Minerva, 72-82.

1935

George Kingsley Zipf (January 7, 1902 – September 25, 1950), was an American linguist and philologist who studied statistical occurrences in different languages.

1935: 乔治·金斯利·齐普夫 (George Kingsley Zipf, 1902-1950) 出版了《语言的心理生物学》，首次明确阐述的“齐普夫定律” (Zipf, 1935)。

ZIPF GK, 1935. The Psycho-biology of Language[M]. Oxford: Houghton-Mifflin.

1936

1936: 赫尔塞·卡森和马塞拉·卢博茨基首次分析了心理学期刊间的交叉引用网络(Cason et al., 1936)

TABLE 2
THE INFLUENCE AND DEPENDENCE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL JOURNALS ON EACH OTHER

JOURNALS	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.	13.
1. <i>Brit. J. P., Gener. Sect.</i>		1.8	.7	.5	2.3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
2. <i>Amer. J. P.</i>	—	1.1	1.8	1.1	1.1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
3. <i>J. Gener. P.</i>	4	9.3	—	2.4	6.4	2.1	9.3	4.9	—	—	—	—	—
4. <i>P. Bull.</i>	2.6	5.2	1.4	—	3.9	1.6	3.9	1.7	—	—	—	—	—
5. <i>P. Rev.</i>	1.5	4.4	1.5	1.3	—	.6	3.4	1.9	—	—	—	—	—
6. <i>Arch. of P.</i>	4.5	4.5	2	2.5	3.6	—	3.0	1.8	3	2	—	3.1	1.3
7. <i>J. Exper. P.</i>	3.2	9.9	4.8	1.1	4.6	1.9	—	3.6	1.9	1.9	2	2.7	4
8. <i>P. Monog.</i>	9	7.5	9	.6	3.5	1.2	6.6	—	3.5	4.6	3	4.6	9
9. <i>J. Physiol.</i>	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	7.2	1.1	—	—	—
10. <i>Amer. J. Physiol.</i>	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	7.2	1.1	—	—	—
11. <i>Physiol. Reus.</i>	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.5	5.8	—	—	8
12. <i>J. Comp. P.</i>	5	4.1	7	2.0	3.7	.5	2.8	2.3	8	3.9	3	—	7
13. <i>Genet. P. Monog.</i>	4	2.2	7	1.6	3.7	7	3.1	.6	7	1.5	1	4.7	—
14. <i>Ped. Sem. & J. Genet. P.</i>	4	2.5	7	2.5	2.9	1.0	2.7	2.6	—	—	—	7.1	1.7
15. <i>Child Develop.</i>	4.1	1.0	—	2.7	1.4	1.7	7	—	3	—	—	1.0	3.1
16. <i>Int. J. Psycho-Anal.</i>	9	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
17. <i>Psychoanal. Rev.</i>	—	3	3	—	3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
18. <i>Brit. J. Med. P.</i>	2.2	7	2	2.2	—	7	1.5	—	—	—	—	—	—
19. <i>Amer. J. Psychiat.</i>	2	1	2	.3	.5	2	2	—	—	—	—	—	—
20. <i>Arch. Neurol. & Psychiat.</i>	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1	2.3	3	—	—
21. <i>J. Nerv. & Ment. Dis.</i>	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5	1.5	2	—	—
22. <i>J. Abn. & Soc. P.</i>	2.4	1.4	7	2.4	3	1.0	7	7	—	—	—	—	7
23. <i>J. Soc. P.</i>	4	2.3	1.9	4.2	1.5	1.5	1.9	—	—	—	—	1.5	—
24. <i>J. Appl. P.</i>	3	1.0	3	1.8	3.1	.5	.8	—	3	—	—	1.8	1.0
25. <i>Brit. J. Educ. P.</i>	9.1	1.0	—	.5	1.4	—	.5	—	—	—	—	—	—
26. <i>J. Educ. P.</i>	6.0	2.1	—	2	2.7	.4	.4	2.7	—	—	—	—	—
27. <i>J. Educ. Res.</i>	9	1.2	2	4	—	.4	1.3	—	—	—	—	—	—
28. <i>T. C. Contr. to Educ.</i>	2	2	1	—	1	—	1	3	—	—	—	—	—
Number of Journals.....	21	23	(19)	18	22	21	21	19	13	18	(10)	16	(15)
Med. Percentage.....	9	2.1	(7)	1.5	2.7	7	1.5	1.7	8	1.3	(.3)	1.8	(7)

TABLE 2
THE INFLUENCE AND DEPENDENCE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL JOURNALS ON EACH OTHER

JOURNALS	16.	17.	18.	19.	20.	21.	22.	23.	24.	25.	26.	27.	28.	A.	B.	C.	D.
16. <i>Int. J. Psycho-Anal.</i>		—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
17. <i>Psychoanal. Rev.</i>	—		—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
18. <i>Brit. J. Med. P.</i>	—	—		—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
19. <i>Amer. J. Psychiat.</i>	—	—	—		—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
20. <i>Arch. Neurol. & Psychiat.</i>	—	—	—	—		—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
21. <i>J. Nerv. & Ment. Dis.</i>	—	—	—	—	—		—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
22. <i>J. Abn. & Soc. P.</i>	—	—	—	—	—	—		—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
23. <i>J. Soc. P.</i>	—	—	—	—	—	—	—		—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
24. <i>J. Appl. P.</i>	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—		—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
25. <i>Brit. J. Educ. P.</i>	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—		—	—	—	—	—	—	—
26. <i>J. Educ. P.</i>	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—		—	—	—	—	—	—
27. <i>J. Educ. Res.</i>	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—		—	—	—	—	—
28. <i>T. C. Contr. to Educ.</i>	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—		—	—	—	—
Reference to Same Journal.....	9.4	15.8	74.8	436	17	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	9.4	15.8	74.8	436
Reference to Other Journals on List.....	12.2	16.8	71.0	1,008	20	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	12.2	16.8	71.0	1,008
All Other References.....	6.0	46.9	47.2	735	22	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	6.0	46.9	47.2	735
Total Number of References.....	2.0	42.1	55.9	3,273	24	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2.0	42.1	55.9	3,273
Number of Journals.....	14.3	24.6	61.1	475	18	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	14.3	24.6	61.1	475
Med. Percentage.....	2.6	36.3	61.1	606	22	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2.6	36.3	61.1	606
Reference to Same Journal.....	14.3	43.2	42.5	475	17	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	14.3	43.2	42.5	475
Reference to Other Journals on List.....	4.3	38.3	57.3	347	17	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	4.3	38.3	57.3	347
All Other References.....	19.1	8.5	72.4	2,093	4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	19.1	8.5	72.4	2,093
Total Number of References.....	22.0	8.7	69.4	4,260	3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	22.0	8.7	69.4	4,260
Number of Journals.....	0.7	13.6	85.8	2,877	12	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.7	13.6	85.8	2,877
Med. Percentage.....	20.8	29.3	49.8	614	19	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	20.8	29.3	49.8	614
Reference to Same Journal.....	2.7	32.5	64.8	677	24	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2.7	32.5	64.8	677
Reference to Other Journals on List.....	8.4	33.8	57.8	692	20	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	8.4	33.8	57.8	692
All Other References.....	5.1	34.2	60.7	295	18	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.1	34.2	60.7	295
Total Number of References.....	18.5	4.9	76.6	329	5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	18.5	4.9	76.6	329
Number of Journals.....	2.6	5.6	91.7	303	8	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2.6	5.6	91.7	303
Med. Percentage.....	0.7	17.8	81.5	410	14	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.7	17.8	81.5	410
Reference to Same Journal.....	5.1	15.4	79.5	963	15	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.1	15.4	79.5	963
Reference to Other Journals on List.....	7.6	6.8	85.7	2,912	11	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	7.6	6.8	85.7	2,912
All Other References.....	1.4	10.8	87.8	1,579	10	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.4	10.8	87.8	1,579
Total Number of References.....	7.9	18.9	73.2	291	17	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	7.9	18.9	73.2	291
Number of Journals.....	5.7	38.5	55.7	262	14	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.7	38.5	55.7	262
Med. Percentage.....	12.4	28.2	59.4	387	20	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	12.4	28.2	59.4	387
Reference to Same Journal.....	1.9	16.3	81.8	209	6	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.9	16.3	81.8	209
Reference to Other Journals on List.....	15.2	25.9	58.9	487	15	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	15.2	25.9	58.9	487
All Other References.....	4.5	17.2	78.3	1,035	17	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	4.5	17.2	78.3	1,035
Total Number of References.....	2.1	5.7	92.3	2,947	14	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2.1	5.7	92.3	2,947
Number of Journals.....	(5)	(6)	(9)	13	18	11	18	(16)	15	(6)	19	(14)	10	(5)	(6)	(9)	13
Med. Percentage.....	(.1)	2	(.3)	.5	.4	.3	.8	(.5)	1.0	(.8)	2.1	(.3)	.9	5.9	18.4	70.2	.8

CASON H, LUBOTSKY M, 1936. The influence and dependence of psychological journals on each other[J]. Psychological Bulletin, 33(2) :95-103.

1939

1939: 约翰·戴斯蒙德·贝尔纳（John Desmond Bernal , 1901-1971）出版了《科学的社会功能》，被认为是首部科学社会学著作(Bernal, 1939)。

John Desmond Bernal FRS(10 May 1901 – 15 September 1971) was an Irish scientist who pioneered the use of X-ray crystallography in molecular biology. He published extensively on the history of science. In addition, Bernal wrote popular books on science and society. He was a communist activist and a member of the Communist Party of Great Britain (CPGB).

BERNAL JD, 1939. The social function of science[M]. London: Routledge

1945

AS WE MAY THINK

by VANNEVAR BUSH

As Director of the Office of Scientific Research and Development, Dr. VANNEVAR BUSH has coordinated the activities of some six thousand leading American scientists in the application of science to warfare. In this significant article he holds up an incentive for scientists when the fighting has ceased. He urges that men of science should then turn to the massive task of making more accessible our bewildering store of knowledge. For years inventions have extended man's physical powers rather than the powers of his mind. Trip hammers that multiply the data, microscopes that sharpen the eye, and engines of destruction and detection are new results, but not the end result, of modern science. Now, says Dr. Bush, instruments are at hand which, if properly developed, will give man access to and command over the inherited knowledge of the ages. The perfection of these precise instruments should be the first objective of our scientists as they emerge from their war work. Like Emerson's famous address of 1837 on "The American Scholar," this paper by Dr. Bush calls for a new relationship between thinking man and the sum of our knowledge. — THE EDITOR

There has not been a scientist's war; it has been a war in which all have had a part. The scientists, burying their old professional competition in the demand of a common cause, have shared greatly and learned much. It has been exhilarating to work in effective partnership. Now, for many, this appears to be approaching an end. What are the scientists to do next?

For the biologists, and particularly for the medical scientists, there can be little indecision, for their war work has hardly required them to leave the old paths. Many indeed have been able to carry on their war research in their familiar peacetime laboratories. Their objectives remain much the same.

It is the physicists who have been thrown most violently off stride, who have left academic pursuits for the making of strange destructive gadgets, who have had to devise new methods for their manufacturing assignments. They have done their part on the part of the enemy. They have worked in combined effort with the physicists of our allies. They have felt within themselves the stir of achievement. They have been part of a great team. Now, as peace approaches, one asks where they will find objectives worthy of their best.

Of what lasting benefit has been man's use of science and of the new instruments which his research brought into existence? First, they have increased his control of his material environment. They have improved his food, his clothing, his shelter; they have increased his security and released him partly from the bondage of mere existence. They have given him increased know-

ledge of his own biological processes so that he has had a progressive freedom from disease and an increased span of life. They are illuminating the interactions of his physiological and psychological functions, giving the promise of an improved mental health. Science has provided the swiftest communication between individuals; it has provided a record of ideas and has enabled man to manipulate and to make extracts from that record so that knowledge evolves and endures throughout the life of a race rather than that of an individual.

There is a growing mountain of research. But there is increased evidence that we are being bogged down today as specialization extends. The investigator is staggered by the findings and conclusions of thousands of other workers — conclusions which he cannot find time to grasp, much less to remember, as they appear. Yet specialization becomes increasingly necessary for progress, and the effort to bridge between disciplines is correspondingly superficial.

Professionally our methods of transmitting and reviewing the results of research are generations old and by now are totally inadequate for their purpose. If the aggregate time spent in writing scholarly works and in reading them could be evaluated, the ratio between these amounts of time might well be startling. Those who conscientiously attempt to keep abreast of current thought, even in restricted fields, by close and continuous reading might well shy away from an examination calculated to show how much of the previous month's efforts could be produced on call. Mendel's concept of the laws of genetics was lost to the world for a generation because his publication did not reach the few who were capable of grasping and extending it; and this sort of catastrophe is undoubtedly being repeated all about us, as truly significant

1945: 范内瓦·布什 (Vannevar Bush, 1890-1974) 发表《诚如所思》(As We May Think), 最早提出通过计算机来检索相关信息的想法 (Vannevar, 1945)。

Vannevar Bush (March 11, 1890 – June 28, 1974) was an American engineer, inventor and science administrator, who during World War II headed the U.S. Office of Scientific Research and Development (OSRD), through which almost all wartime military R&D was carried out, including important developments in radar and the initiation and early administration of the Manhattan Project. He emphasized the importance of scientific research to national security and economic well-being, and was chiefly responsible for the movement that led to the creation of the National Science Foundation.

As We May Think

“Consider a future device ... in which an individual stores all his books, records, and communications, and which is mechanized so that it may be consulted with exceeding speed and flexibility. It is an enlarged intimate supplement to his memory.”

By Vannevar Bush

BUSH V, 1945. As we may think[J]. The atlantic monthly, 176(1) :101-108.

1948

1948：萨缪尔·克莱门特·布拉德福（Samuel Clement Bradford, 1878-1948）出版了他的著作《文献学》(Bradford, 1948)，收录了1934年的论文，为唤醒布拉德福定律的价值和传播发挥了重要作用。

Samuel Clement Bradford (10 January 1878 in London – 13 November 1948) was a British mathematician, librarian and documentalist at the Science Museum in London. He developed "Bradford's law" (or the "law of scattering") regarding differences in demand for scientific journals

BRADFORD SC, 1948. Documentation[M]. London: Crosby Lockwood.

1948

Claude Elwood Shannon (April 30, 1916 – February 24, 2001) was an American mathematician, electrical engineer, computer scientist and cryptographer known as the "father of information theory" and as the "father of the Information Age."

1948: 香农 (Claude Elwood Shannon, 1916-2001) 发表了《通信的数学理论》 (A Mathematical Theory of Communication) (Shannon, 1948a,b)。

SHANNON CE, 1948a. A mathematical theory of communication[J]. Bell System Technical Journal, 27(3):379-423.
SHANNON CE, 1948b. A mathematical theory of communication[J]. Bell System Technical Journal, 27(4): 623-656.

1948

1948: 拉冈纳坦（Shiyali Ramamrita Ranganathan, 1892-1972, 被称为印度图书馆之父）提出了“图书计量学（librametrics）”，但该文未公开发表。

RANGANATHAN, SHIYALI RAMAMRITA (1892-1972)

S. R. Ranganathan is considered by many to be the foremost theorist in the field of classification because of his contributions to the theory of facet analysis. In addition to being known as the "Father of Library Science" in India, his accomplishments include founding the Documentation Research and Training Centre in Bangalore, India; developing his Five Laws of Library Science (1931) and Colon Classification (1933); and authoring more than sixty books and two thousand articles.

1949

George Kingsley Zipf (January 7, 1902 – September 25, 1950), was an American linguist and philologist who studied statistical occurrences in different languages.

1949：乔治·金斯利·齐普夫（George Kingsley Zipf, 1902-1950）出版了他的书《人类行为与最小努力原则》，总结了他在词频分布理论研究中的主要观点 (Zipf, 1949)。

ZIPF GK, 1949. Human Behavior and the Principle of Least Effort. An Introduction to Human Ecology[M]. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Addison-Wesley Press Inc.

1954

1954: 本华·曼德博 (Benoit Mandelbrot, 1924 -2010, 创造了分形几何) 出版了《文本的形式结构与交流》(Structure formelle des textes et communication), 其中, 包含了曼德尔布罗特定律 (Mandelbrot, 1954)。

Benoit B.Mandelbrot(20 November 1924 – 14 October 2010) was a Polish-born French-American mathematician and polymath with broad interests in the practical sciences, especially regarding what he labeled as "the art of roughness" of physical phenomena and "the uncontrolled element in life". He referred to himself as a "fractalist" and is recognized for his contribution to the field of fractal geometry, which included coining the word "fractal", as well as developing a theory of "roughness and self-similarity" in nature.

MANDELBROT B, 1954. Structure formelle des textes et communication: Deux études par[J]. Word, 10(1), 1-27.

1955

1955: 加菲尔德（Eugene Eli Garfield, 1925 – 2017）提出了科学引文索引的想法(Garfield, 1955).

Eugene Eli Garfield (September 16, 1925 – February 26, 2017) was an American linguist and businessman, one of the founders of bibliometrics and scientometrics. He helped to create Current Contents, Science Citation Index (SCI), Journal Citation Reports, and Index Chemicus, among others, and founded the magazine *The Scientist*.

GARFIELD E, 1955. Citation indexes for science: A new dimension in documentation through association of ideas[J]. *Science*, 122(3159):108-111.

1956

1956: 罗伯特·法诺（Roberto Mario Fano, 1917 - 2016, 麻省理工学院教授）提出了引文耦合（Bibliographic coupling）的想法（Fano, 1956）。

Roberto Mario "Robert" Fano (11 November 1917 – 13 July 2016) was an Italian-American computer scientist and professor of electrical engineering and computer science at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. He became a student and working lab partner to Claude Shannon, whom he admired zealously and assisted in the early years of Information Theory.

FANO RM, 1956. Information theory and the retrieval of recorded information. In J. H. Shera, A. Kent, & J. W. Perry (Eds.), *Documentation in action*[M]. New York: Reinhold Publ. Co. 238-244.

1958

1958：约翰·戴斯蒙德·贝尔纳（John Desmond Bernal，1901-1971）在《科学信息传播：用户分析》的会议论文中提出了文献的半衰期（Bernal, 1958）。

John Desmond Bernal FRS(10 May 1901 – 15 September 1971) was an Irish scientist who pioneered the use of X-ray crystallography in molecular biology. He published extensively on the history of science. In addition, Bernal wrote popular books on science and society. He was a communist activist and a member of the Communist Party of Great Britain (CPGB).

BERNAL JD, 1958. The transmission of scientific information: a user's analysis[C]. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Scientific Information, 1 (1960) :77-95.

1960

1960: 伯顿 (R. E. Burton, 图书管理员) 和凯布勒 (R. W. Kebler, 物理学家) 在信息科学文献中深入讨论了半衰期的概念(Burton et al., 1960)。

THE "HALF-LIFE" OF SOME SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL LITERATURES

R. E. BURTON* and R. W. KEBLER**

ABSTRACT

A consideration of the analogy between the half-life of radioactive substances and the rate of obsolescence of scientific literature. The validity of this analogy suggests the possibility of more accurate prognostications concerning the period of time during which scientific literature may be used and hence might help to guide the planning of library collections and technical information services.

The concept of half-life is most familiar to the physicist and nuclear engineer who employ it to describe the decay of radioactive substances. Recently, however, the expression has been used by documentalists, some librarians, and other information "officers" to describe a totally different measure in a manner which implies a rather rigid analogy. The term was much in evidence at the International Conference on Scientific Information meetings in Washington in November, 1958. Unfortunately, unlike the physicists' use of the expression, which is bounded by a precise definition, the documentalists' use has been imprecise, unverified by evidence, and generally subject to criticism. It is the purpose of this paper to examine the applicability of a half-life analogy to scientific literature, and to provide at least a small amount of data on which to base certain conclusions.

The physical scientists' concept of half-life is that of a decay function wherein the degree of radioactivity, or the intensity of the radiation, is measured against time. To borrow the definition used in one of the standard references, (1) half-life is the "time required for disintegration of one-half the atoms of a sample of a radioactive substance." The plot of such a function, that for uranium 239, is shown in Figure 1. The half-life is 23.5 minutes.

One point of special interest is that the half-life periods are of equal duration. That is, at any given time, the half-life of the

remaining material is the same as the half-life of the original mass.

Fig. 1. Decay Curve for Uranium 239

The approach to the term half-life in relation to scientific literature is somewhat different. A working definition, closely analogous

to radioactive half-life is that it is that time required for the obsolescence of one-half the currently published literature. Unfortunately, this obsolescence time cannot be precisely measured. Unlike a radioactive substance, which becomes something entirely different on disintegration, literature simply becomes unused, but not unusable. It is obsolescent, but not "disintegrated."

There are further difficulties. One could take a sample of scientific literature published this year and attempt, over the next two or three decades, to measure the rate at which it becomes obsolete. This could be done if agreement could be reached on a definition of "obsolescent" and if one had the patience to wait thirty or forty years.

If, however, one redefines the use of half-life in this sense and if he describes what has occurred in the past, he can obtain a useful measure of a quantity which resembles a half-life in many respects. The revised working definition then becomes the time during which one-half of all the currently active literature was published. This is saying, then, that one-half of all the active literature of a subject field was published not more than this time, $T_{1/2}$, ago. The determination of this quantity is possible and can be obtained with some reliability. Other studies, (2,3) particularly those on citations in periodical literature, have collected data which can be used for the determination. A generalized curve for this second definition is given in Figure 2. Figure 3 is a generalized curve of the type in Figure 1 as it would apply to literature, i.e., in accord with the first definition, the rate of obsolescence. For the work in this paper curves shall be used of the type in Figure 2, as they are a more descriptive representation of the data actually used.

Nine engineering and scientific fields have been investigated in this paper. Three engineering fields utilized data in the paper by Burton (4) and six science fields used data in Brown's book, (5) Zoology and entomology, which were included in the Brown study, were not used here because the nature of literature use in these areas seemed to need more study. The nine areas studied were chemical engineering, mechanical engineering, metallurgical engineering, mathematics, physics, chemistry, geology, physiology, and botany. The present paper is concerned with only the longevity of periodical literature.

Fig. 2. Generalized Active Literature Curve

Both Burton and Brown collected data based on citation counts in selected source journals. The citations were distributed in various ways, one of which was time. Both studies utilized ten year periods and, while the periods selected are not the same, the data are comparable.

The data, which in the original studies showed the percentage of citations which fell within a particular decade, were reworked to show the cumulative percentages which fell in the ranges of one decade, two decades, and so on. For example, in the field of chemical engineering 75% of all citations had been published within the last ten years and 13% in the previous ten years. Thus 88% of the references had been

Field	Decades				
	1	1-2	1-3	1-4	1-5
Chemical Engineering	75	88	96	-	-
Mechanical Engineering	72	87	94	-	-
Metallurgical Engineering	82	93	97	-	-
Mathematics	48	77	89	94	98
Physics	78	82	88	99	100
Chemistry	58	77	87	91	95
Geology	42	80	84	90	94
Physiology	62	84	94	97	99
Botany	50	79	90	94	97

Fig. 3. Generalized Literature Obsolescence Curve

published in the last two decades. The complete cumulated percentages are given in Table I.

The next step in the determination of a literature half-life for the fields considered was to plot curves similar to that given in Figure 2 for each set of data. It was immediately observed that the curves were very similar and were exponential in character. An attempt was made, therefore, to determine the best exponential type curve for each field, so that half-lives could be calculated, as well as determined from observation. The authors found that the following type of curve fitted the experimental data.

$$y = 1 - \left(\frac{a}{e^{bx}} + \frac{b}{e^{bx}} \right)$$

where $a + b = 1$; y = cumulated percentage expressed as a decimal; x = time in decades.

The curve also satisfied the boundary conditions of $x = 0, y = 0$ (citations are not made to references not yet published) $x = \infty, y = 1$ (all citations are included in all references published)

Curves were fitted to the data in each of the nine subject areas, and x value corresponding to $y = 0.5$ was calculated. The results of these calculations are shown in Table II and the curves are shown in Figs. 4-12.

Table II
Literature Half-Lives

Chemical Engineering	4.6 years
Mechanical Engineering	5.2
Metallurgical Engineering	3.9
Mathematics	10.5
Physics	4.6
Chemistry	8.1
Geology	11.8
Physiology	7.3
Botany	10.0

Because of the necessity of using a function with two exponential terms in order to describe the data, the half-lives calculated at points greater than $y = 0.5$, for example, at $y = 0.75, 0.875$, and so on, did not agree with the half-life calculated at $y = 0.5$. This disagreement arises from the nature of the data, but an analogy with radioactive half-lives still can be drawn.

Given a sample of radioactive material made up of two or more radioactive substances, the physicist finds that the decay curve is actually compounded of a series of components of varying half-lives. (6) Some components may have very short half-lives and others very long half-lives. The result, of course, is a curve in which the half-life periods vary.

It is possible that the periodical literature of a subject field is similarly composed of two or more distinct types of literature each having its own half-life. There is, for example, in most fields, a body of literature which is referred to as the classic literature. Presumably this classic literature has a relatively longer half-life than so-called ephemeral literature such as is found in weekly news publications. Certainly this problem should be more thoroughly investigated.

In drawing some of the curves using the raw data, it was suspected that the curve would move upwards rather slowly in the range of 0-3 years. This is similar in Figure 13. If this is, indeed, true, the principal explanation is probably to be found in the fact that there is a necessary lag in the time between the publication of an article and the earliest possible publication of a reference to it. It might prove interesting to investigate the extent of this lag.

The usefulness of data concerning the half-life of scientific and technological periodical literature is to be found primarily in the areas of administration of literature collections or libraries. If, for example, 75% of the useful physics literature was published within a ten

BURTON RE, KEBLER RW, 1960. The "half-life" of some scientific and technical literatures[J]. American Documentation, 11(1), 1822.

*Librarian, Union Carbide Metals Co., Niagara Falls, N. Y.
**Development Physicist, Speedway Laboratories, Lindo Co., Indianapolis, Ind.

1960

1960: 加菲尔德（Eugene Eli Garfield, 1925-2017）博士成立了美国科学信息研究所（Institute for Scientific Information）。

1962

Bibliographic Coupling Between Scientific Papers¹

Received 7 August 1962

M. M. KESSLER

Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Cambridge, Massachusetts

A previous report described a new method for grouping technical and scientific papers on the basis of bibliographic coupling units. A single item of reference used by two papers was defined as a unit of coupling between them. Based on this unit, two graded criteria of coupling were defined.²

Criterion A: A number of papers constitute a related group G_A if each member of the group has at least one coupling unit to a given test paper P_o . The coupling strength between P_o and any member of G_A is measured by the number of coupling units (n) between them. G_A^2 is that portion of G_A that is linked to P_o through n coupling units.

Criterion B: A number of papers constitute a related group G_B if each member of the group has at least one coupling unit to every other member of the group.

A computer program was written to process a large number of scientific articles into groups that satisfy Criterion A.³ The population of papers under study consisted of 36 volumes of the *Physical Review* (Vols. 77 to 112 inclusive). These volumes contained 8,521 articles which generated 137,000 references to 795 separate sources.⁴ From each article in this range of the *Physical Review* the following information was extracted and put on magnetic tape:

1. Volume and page number on which the article begins

¹Supported by a grant from the National Science Foundation to the Massachusetts Institute of Technology Libraries.

²The possibility of grouping scientific papers on the basis of use rather than content was suggested by Professor R. M. Fano in *Documentation in Action*, 1956, chapter XIV-a, pp. 238-244. Reinhold Publishing Corp., New York; and independently by the present author in Concerning some problems of intrascience communication, 1958, *Lincoln Laboratory Group Report 45-35*, 8 December.

³I wish to acknowledge the assistance of Mr. David Friedman and Mr. Armen Gabriellan who wrote the program for the IBM 709 computer.

⁴Preliminary statistics on the source material were published in M. M. Kessler, Technical information flow patterns, 1961. *Proc. Western Joint Computer Conference*, pp. 247-257. A detailed analysis is being prepared.

2. Title
3. Author(s)
4. All bibliographic data in the form
 - a. Title of journal or other source (coded by number)
 - b. Volume number (if periodical)
 - c. Page number

This data completely identifies each bibliographic item except for the rare case of two papers starting on the same page. When that happens, the computer will interpret the two papers as identical and thus introduce false couplings into the group. Although a few errors due to this anomaly were found in our results, it is a rare phenomenon that will be corrected in future work.

Let us call P_m the population of papers being examined and P_o the test paper. Several strategies are available for the ordering of members of P_m according to Criterion A.

1. One or more papers outside of P_m may serve as P_o 's, and all or part of P_m may be processed. Example: Search *Physical Review*, 1958, for papers that match a given paper.
2. Part of P_m may constitute P_o 's and all or part of the remaining P_m may be searched. Example: Search the past five years of the *Physical Review* for papers that match certain papers in the latest number.
3. All or part of P_m may be arranged into related groups, each item of P_m serving in turn as P_o for all the others. Example: Arrange a given volume of *Physical Review* into related groups.

The results of such processing applied to our entire set of P_m , 8,521 papers, are clearly too voluminous to be presented in a report. We give here the detailed results of strategy 3 applied to Volume 97 of the *Physical Review*. The volume contains 265 articles (see Table 1). Each article in this volume was treated as P_o , and the remaining 264 as P_m . Thus 265 G_A 's were generated. A

1962/1963: 迈克尔·凯斯勒 (Michael M. Kessler, 麻省理工大学) 提出并系统研究了文献耦合 (Bibliographic coupling) 的概念及其应用(Kessler, 1962; Kessler, 1963)。

KESSLER M M, 1962. An experimental study of bibliographic coupling between technical papers. M. I.T. Report R-I, November.
KESSLER M M, 1963. Bibliographic coupling between scientific papers[J]. *American Documentation*, 14(1):10-25.

1963

1963: 《科学引文索引》（Science Citation Index）第一版发布 (Garfield, 1963).

Eugene Eli Garfield (September 16, 1925 – February 26, 2017) was an American linguist and businessman, one of the founders of bibliometrics and scientometrics. He helped to create Current Contents, Science Citation Index (SCI), Journal Citation Reports, and Index Chemicus, among others, and founded the magazine The Scientist.

GARFIELD E, 1963. Science citation index. An international interdisciplinary index to the literature of science[M]. Philadelphia: Institute for Scientific information.

1963

1963: 普赖斯（Derek John de Solla Price, 1922 - 1983）发表了《小科学，大科学》（Little science, big science）(Price, 1963).

Derek John de Solla Price (22 January 1922 – 3 September 1983) was a British physicist, historian of science, and information scientist. He was known for his investigation of the Antikythera mechanism, an ancient Greek planetary computer, and for quantitative studies on scientific publications, which led to his being described as the "Herald of scientometrics".

PRICE D J D S, 1963. Little science, big science[M]. Columbia University Press.

1963

1963: 加菲尔德 (Eugene Eli Garfield, 1925 - 2017) 和欧文·舍尔 (Irving H. Sher, 1924–1996) 提出期刊的影响因子 (Journal Impact Factor) (Garfield, 2001; Garfield, 2005)。

Eugene Eli Garfield (September 16, 1925 – February 26, 2017) was an American linguist and businessman, one of the founders of bibliometrics and scientometrics. He helped to create Current Contents, Science Citation Index (SCI), Journal Citation Reports, and Index Chemicus, among others, and founded the magazine *The Scientist*.

GARFIELD E, 2001. Recollections of Irving H. Sher 1924–1996: polymath/information scientist extraordinaire[J]. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 52(14):1197-1202.

GARFIELD E, 2005. The agony and the ecstasy—the history and meaning of the journal impact factor[J]. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 295(1):22.

1964: 威廉·戈夫曼 (William Goffman) 及其同事引入了疾病流行病学概念, 用以模拟知识的传播, 包括科学发现的动态 (Goffman et al., 1964)。

GENERALIZATION OF EPIDEMIC THEORY AN APPLICATION TO THE TRANSMISSION OF IDEAS

By Dr. WILLIAM GOFFMAN
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Western Reserve University,
AND
Dr. VAUN A. NEWILL
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ONE of the most fundamental problems in the field of information retrieval is that of determining the circumstances under which it might be necessary to introduce an information retrieval system as an aid to a given population of scientists. It is proposed that this problem be examined in terms of the transmission and development of ideas within a population. Specifically, the transmission of ideas within a population will be treated as if it were the transmission of an infectious disease, that is, in terms of an epidemic process. An attempt will be made to indicate the role of information retrieval in the development of such a process.

The Epidemic Model

Since the spread of disease in a population is to be our model for the transmission of ideas, it is appropriate to discuss the essential principles pertinent to this issue. These principles are a part of epidemiology. The necessary elements involved in the process of the spread of an infectious disease are those of: (1) a specified population; (2) an exposure to infectious material. The members of the population belong to 1 of 3 basic classes at a given instant in time: (a) *infectives*, those members who are host to the infectious material; (b) *susceptibles*, those who can become infectives given contact with infectious material; (c) *removals*, those who have been removed for one of a variety of reasons such as death, immunity, hospitalization, etc. These latter members may have been either susceptibles or infectives at the time of their removal.

The entire process is time-dependent, that is, a sequence of events occurs which describes the process. An individual is exposed to infectious material either by direct contact with an infective or through some intermediary host or vector. The exposed person may either be resistant to the incoming organism, in which case the material is rejected, or may be infected by it, in which case the invading organism proceeds on a course of development. The time interval in which the development takes place is called the 'latency period' (or incubation period), that is, the interval of time necessary for a susceptible to be transformed into an infective. In other words, the latency period is the time between the receipt of infectious material by a susceptible and the time at which he is in position to transmit infectious material to another susceptible, thus repeating the process. An epidemic occurs when the process of susceptibles being transformed to infectives crosses a certain threshold. (The American Public Health Association (1960) defined an epidemic as "the occurrence in a community... of a group of illnesses of similar nature, clearly in excess of normal expectation.")

The process already described here does not take into account the almost endless number of complexities which actually arise. It is a model, that is, an idealization of the real situation in which the complex process is reduced to its essential properties.

Transmission of Ideas as an 'Epidemic' Process

In general, the 'epidemic' process can be characterized as one of transition from one state (susceptible) to another (infective) where the transition is caused by exposure to some phenomenon (infectious material). The process need not be restricted to infectious disease but is a more general abstract process that might be applied to many situations. All that is needed is the appropriate inter-duced into the host (N_1) and vector (N_2) populations at time t_0 , that is, $N_1 = (S_0, 1, 0)$ and $N_2 = (S_2^0, 1, 0)$. For an epidemic to develop from time t_0 , the change in the number of infectives in both the host and vector populations must be positive. Hence, from the above differential equations, we obtain the threshold $\rho\rho'$ as follows:

Table 2. STATES OF TRANSITION OF THE HOST AND VECTOR POPULATIONS*
State to which an individual belongs
At time t At time $t + \Delta t$
(1) Susceptible Susceptible, infective or removal
(2) Infective Infective or removal
(3) Removal Removal

* In general the host and vector populations need not follow the same transitional patterns as in this case.

or removal, the infective can remain an infective or become a removal, and the removal must remain a removal (Table 2). (To keep the mathematical model simple in this presentation, we are not permitting immunes to lose their immunity and to return to the susceptible population.) The latency period is assumed to be zero so that infectives occur continuously with time. If we assume homogeneous mixing among the members of the populations, the total process can be deterministically described by the following systems of differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dS}{dt} &= -\beta S'I - \delta S + \mu & \frac{dS'}{dt} &= -\beta'S'I - \delta S' + \mu' \\ \frac{dI}{dt} &= \beta S'I - \gamma I + \nu & \frac{dI'}{dt} &= \beta'S'I - \gamma'I + \nu' \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= \gamma I + \delta S & \frac{dR'}{dt} &= \gamma'I + \delta'S' \end{aligned}$$

A threshold density of susceptibles can be obtained if we assume initial conditions of a single infective introduced into the host (N_1) and vector (N_2) populations at time t_0 , that is, $N_1 = (S_0, 1, 0)$ and $N_2 = (S_2^0, 1, 0)$. For an epidemic to develop from time t_0 , the change in the number of infectives in both the host and vector populations must be positive. Hence, from the above differential equations, we obtain the threshold $\rho\rho'$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \beta S'I &> \gamma I - \nu \\ \beta'S'I &> \gamma'I - \nu' \\ \text{or } \beta\beta'S_0S_2^0 &> \gamma\gamma' - \nu\nu' - \gamma\nu + \nu\nu' \\ \text{and } S_0S_2^0 &> \left(\frac{\gamma - \nu}{\beta}\right)\left(\frac{\gamma' - \nu'}{\beta'}\right) = \rho\rho' \end{aligned}$$

where $\frac{\gamma - \nu}{\beta} = \rho$; and $\frac{\gamma' - \nu'}{\beta'} = \rho'$

The epidemic curve which traces the development of the epidemic in time is given by the differential equation $\frac{dI}{dt} = F(t)$ with peaks at the points in time where $\frac{d^2I}{dt^2} = 0$. The size of the epidemic is given by the limit of I as t goes to infinity, that is, the size of the infective population I after a long period of time. This discussion indicates that an epidemic can only develop from time t_0 provided that the product of the host and vector susceptible population exceeds the threshold $\rho\rho'$. When a potential epidemic condition is present, the quantity of scientists and information is sufficiently large that given effective contact an epidemic can develop. It is at this time that an information retrieval system might be introduced.

If the population is already in an epidemic state, an information retrieval system can be introduced in order to maintain or increase the frequency of effective contacts between susceptibles and infectives. Hence, the points at which an information retrieval system might be usefully introduced into a population are either at the initial point or the peak of the epidemic process or at a time when intensification of the epidemic process is desired. Other models different from the one we have presented could be constructed that would interpret the epidemic in a different manner. For example, a model can be elaborated by introducing two interacting populations with rates of migration from one population to the other. One population might consist of biostatisticians and the

other of epidemiologists. The 'disease' could be statistical epidemiology. Then one might study the development of the field in terms of the interacting host and vector populations rather than in terms of single populations.

The Stochastic Approach

In a stochastic model of the process described above the actual number of new infectives occurring in a short time interval would be replaced with the probability of a new case occurring in that interval. This type of mathematical treatment is particularly applicable when dealing with small populations.

An epidemic process within a large population can be characterized as a collection of epidemic processes within sub-populations. For example, the outbreak of an infectious disease in a community might more specifically be studied in terms of the household populations rather than the community as a whole. Similarly the intellectual epidemic process within the population of a certain discipline could be studied in terms of its sub-populations, that is, the 'disease' I of field F might be studied in terms of the sub-fields of F , indicating, from the point of view of information retrieval, where intellectual epidemics are developing in a given discipline.

Thus, a stochastic treatment of the epidemic processes would in general be more desirable because the size of the populations being studied has been reduced. Unfortunately a stochastic model of an epidemic process with a vector population does not exist so far as we know. Such a model is in need of development and attention is being given to this problem by the authors.

Deterministic models, however, can be very useful, particularly in dealing with large populations, and experiments have been designed for the purpose of testing the model presented above.

Discussion

The construction of a mathematical model of a complex physical situation involves a certain amount of simplification. This is because the purpose of the mathematical model is the description and prediction of the essential patterns of the physical process and not the achievement of its complete analysis.

A total understanding of the process requires studies complementary to the mathematical ones. In the case of the infectious diseases this means biological, ecological, and clinical investigations of the process as well as mathematical and linguistic studies.

Mathematics cannot indicate why exposure to a certain virus will lead to infection or why a certain article will infect the reader with an idea. These important questions must be answered elsewhere. However, mathematics can make important contributions toward an understanding of the epidemic process if one keeps its limitations in mind.

Of course, the usefulness of a mathematical model depends on: (1) being able to solve the model; (2) obtaining reliable measurements in order to test it. These are by no means negligible problems, since even the most simple representations present difficulties in obtaining algebraic solutions. This is particularly true of the stochastic case. Additional problems are encountered in relation to defining populations and obtaining reliable estimates of the parameters of the process.

Although implementation of the epidemic model presents certain difficulties, much useful information concerning the transmission of ideas within a population might be obtained from the mathematical approach. It could help in answering several questions that are basic for the design and operation of information retrieval systems. These questions include: (1) Where and when is activity within a given discipline developing into 'epidemic' proportions? (2) What is the expected

1965

1965: 普赖斯（Derek John de Solla Price, 1922 - 1983）发表了《科学论文的网络》，是早期科学论文网络分析研究的经典之作（Price, 1965）。

Derek John de Solla Price (22 January 1922 – 3 September 1983) was a British physicist, historian of science, and information scientist. He was known for his investigation of the Antikythera mechanism, an ancient Greek planetary computer, and for quantitative studies on scientific publications, which led to his being described as the "Herald of scientometrics".

PRICE D J D S, 1965. Networks of scientific papers[J]. Science, 149:510-15.

1966

1966:瓦西里·瓦西列维奇·纳利莫夫（Vasiliy Vasilevich Nalimov, 1910-1997）等提出了“科学计量学（naukometriya）”（Nalimov et al., 1969）。

Vasiliy Vasilievich Nalimov (Васи́лий Васи́льевич На́лимов; 4 November 1910, Moscow – 19 January 1997) was a Russian philosopher and humanist and wrote on Transpersonal Psychology. Nalimov has a reputation as a founder of the area of Scientometrics, as he coined the Russian term "Naukometriya" in 1969, together with Mulchenko. He was not proposing the concept of citation index, as sometimes claimed. That idea reaches much further back (1873) and was first professionally used in the area of law to look up related cases Shepard's Citations. It was introduced on a large scale for science first by Eugene Garfield.

NALIMOV VV, 1966. Kolichestvennye metody issledovaniya protsessa razvitiya nauki[J]. Voprosy filosofii, 12:38-47.

NALIMOV VV, MUL'CHENKO ZM, 1969. Наукометрия, Изучение развития Науки как информационного процесса [Naukometriya, the Study of the Development of Science as an Information Process] (in Russian) [M]. Moscow: Nauka.

1966

Karl Erik Rosengren, a svédországi Lund kommunikáció egyetem profeszszora .

1966/1968: 罗森格伦 (K.E. Rosengren) 在文学评论中引入了共提及 (comentioning) 的概念, 这在概念上与共引用 (co-citation) 的想法类似 (Rosengren, 1966; Rosengren, 1968) 。

ROSENGREN KE, 1966. The literary system[D]. University of Lund. Lund, Sweden.

ROSENGREN KE, 1968. Sociological aspects of the literary system. Stockholm: Natur och Kultur.

1967

1967: 莱姆库勒函数 (Leimkuhler function) 提出了布拉德福德定律的连续描述 (Leimkuhler, 1967)。

[Ferdinand Leimkuhler](#)

Professor Leimkuhler joined the Purdue faculty in 1961 after graduating from Johns Hopkins University. At Purdue, he taught courses in operations research and engineering economics. He was head of the School of Industrial Engineering from 1969 to 1974 and from 1981 to 1993. In 1980 he was the organizing director of Purdue's Computer Integrated Design, Manufacturing, and Automation Center, and from 1993 to 2000, he directed Purdue's Technical Assistance Program. He led studies of the operations of research libraries for the National Science Foundation from 1962 to 1985, and was a distinguished lecturer for the American Library Association. His book, *An Enduring Quest: The Story of Purdue Industrial Engineers*, was published by Purdue University Press in 2009. He became professor emeritus in 2000 and now lives in Berkeley, California with his wife Natalie and three of his six children. His son Ben is professor of mathematics at the University of Edinburgh, Scotland and his daughter Meg teaches at the University of Colorado.

THE BRADFORD DISTRIBUTION

FERDINAND F. LEIMKUHLER

*Professor of Industrial Engineering, Purdue University,
Lafayette, Indiana*

The distribution of references in a collection of pertinent source documents can be described and predicted by the relation

$$F(x) = \frac{\ln(1 + \beta x)}{\ln(1 + \beta)}$$

where the parameter β is related to the subject field and the completeness of the collection. The model is used to predict the reference yield of abstracting journals in a search for thermophysical property data. It is used also to explain differences among various literature studies of the past in terms of differences in subject and comprehensiveness of search. The model is derived from S. C. Bradford's 'law of scattering' and is called the Bradford Distribution.

INTRODUCTION

THE CURRENT REVOLUTION in computer-aided, micro-analytic techniques of information retrieval was largely justified by earlier studies of the literature used in scientific research. These studies showed that researcher interest was widely scattered among formal titles and classifications and much more extensive than the coverage provided by existing bibliographic services. The most important measure of scatter used in empirical studies is 'title dispersion' which is defined as the degree to which the useful literature of a given subject area is scattered through a number of different books and journals. Stevens³ made a comparative analysis of title dispersion data from eight studies as shown in Table 1. By inspection of this data, he concluded that the dispersion is smaller in pure science, greater in technology, and greatest in the humanities.

Of particular interest is the work of S. C. Bradford.¹ He studied the title dispersion of useful papers in two areas: applied geophysics and lubrication, by arranging the source titles in order of productivity and then dividing them into three approximately equal groups as shown in Table 2. Bradford concluded that the ratios of the titles in successive zones followed a common pattern, and proposed the following 'law of scattering':

If scientific journals are arranged in order of decreasing productivity of articles on a given subject, they may be divided into a nucleus of periodicals more particularly devoted to the subject, and several groups or zones containing the same number of articles as the nucleus, where the

1968

1968: 默顿（Robert King Merton, 1910-2003）提出了科学中的马太效应 (Merton, 1968).

Robert King Merton (born Meyer Robert Schkolnick; July 4, 1910 – February 25, 2003) was an American sociologist who is considered a founding father of modern sociology, and a major contributor to the subfield of criminology. He served as the 47th president of the American Sociological Association. He spent most of his career teaching at Columbia University, where he attained the rank of University Professor. In 1994 he was awarded the National Medal of Science for his contributions to the field and for having founded the sociology of science.

MERTON RK, 1968. The Matthew effect in science: The reward and communication systems of science are considered[J]. Science, 159(3810):56-63.

1968

Francis Narin, 1934-

1968: 弗朗西斯·纳林（Francis Narin, 1934-）创建了计算机地平线公司（Computer Horizons Inc）。

Since founding CHI in 1968, Dr. Francis Narin's work has defined the leading edge of science and technology evaluation. He has led the way through four generations of evaluation work. He started with the analysis of science in the 1970s, before developing evaluations of patents in the 1980s. He then went on to show the links between science and technology in the 1990s, and has recently revealed the relationship between patented technology and stock market performance.

1969

Alan Pritchard (1941-2015)

1969: 艾伦·普里查德 (Alan Pritchard, 1941-2015) 提出了“文献计量学 (bibliometrics)” (Pritchard, 1969).

PRITCHARD A, 1969. Statistical bibliography or bibliometrics? [J]. Journal of Documentation, 25(4):348- 349.

1969

1969: 罗伯特·费尔索恩 (Robert Fairthorne) 提出了文献计量学法则的等价性(Fairthorne, 1969).

The Emerald Research Register for this journal is available at www.emeraldinsight.com/researchregister
The current issue and full text archive of this journal is available at www.emeraldinsight.com/0022-0418.htm

60 YEARS OF THE BEST IN
INFORMATION RESEARCH
PROGRESS IN DOCUMENTATION

Empirical hyperbolic distributions (Bradford-Zipf-Mandelbrot) for bibliometric description and prediction

Robert A. Fairthorne
Farnborough, UK

Empirical
hyperbolic
distributions

171

Abstract

Purpose – Aims to build on the work of Buckland and Hindle regarding statistical distribution as applied to the field of bibliometrics, particularly the use of empirical laws.

Design/methodology/approach – Gives examples of hyperbolic distributions that have a bearing on the bibliometric application, and discusses the characteristics of hyperbolic distributions and the Bradford distribution.

Findings – Hyperbolic distributions are the inevitable result of combinatorial necessity and a tendency to short-term rational behaviour.

Originality/value – Supports Bradford's conclusion from his law, i.e. that to know about one's speciality, one must go outside it.

Keywords Mathematical modelling, Library management

Paper type General review

Since 1960, and especially during the past three years, many papers have appeared about particular manifestations and applications of a certain class of empirical laws to a field that may be labelled conveniently "Bibliometrics". This term, resuscitated by Alan Pritchard, denotes, in my paraphrase, quantitative treatment of the properties of recorded discourse and behaviour appertaining to it.

In this field the law cited is usually that named after Bradford (1934, 1948) or Zipf (1935, 1949) according to whether the interest is in vocabulary or periodical literature

Mr Alan Pritchard was not only the involuntary donor of the term "Bibliometrics", but also the voluntary donor of a most helpful bibliography. Mrs Elizabeth Mack of Aslib, and Messrs Wright and Seymour of the Royal Aircraft Establishment, Farnborough, went well beyond the call of duty in helping me to read what authors had actually written.

Note: This article was previously published in *Journal of Documentation*, Vol. 25 No. 4 pp. 319-343, 1969. It has been included in this issue as part of a series of articles celebrating 60 years of the best in information research in *Journal of Documentation*.

Journal of Documentation
Vol. 61 No. 2, 2005
pp. 171-183
© Emerald Group Publishing Limited
0022-0418
DOI 10.1108/00220410510585179

PROGRESS IN DOCUMENTATION

Empirical Hyperbolic Distributions (Bradford-Zipf-Mandelbrot) for Bibliometric Description and Prediction

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SINCE 1960, and especially during the past three years, many papers have appeared about particular manifestations and applications of a certain class of empirical laws to a field that may be labelled conveniently 'Bibliometrics'. This term, resuscitated by Alan Pritchard (see page 348), denotes, in my paraphrase, quantitative treatment of the properties of recorded discourse and behaviour appertaining to it.

In this field the law cited is usually that named after Bradford^{4,5} or Zipf^{9,60} according to whether the interest is in vocabulary or periodical literature or physical access, in the rate of diminishing returns, or in the cumulative yield from a given input. The behaviour is hyperbolic; that is, the product of fixed powers of the variables is constant. This type of behaviour has been observed for a century or so in fields ranging from meteorology to economics, and has given rise to many particular explanations appropriate to the particular fields. Thus it has received many names according to its exponents, in both senses of that word.

A recent note by Buckland and Hindle¹⁰ and subsequent correspondence^{2,9,52,11,8} have outlined the application of the Zipf-Bradford (rectangular hyperbolic, or harmonic) relation to aspects of library management and aligned it with some cognate studies in other fields.

This paper, and its bibliography, supplement Buckland and Hindle. It aims to help present and future workers to build on what has been done already. To this end I, as have others, interpret earlier work as particular applications of a certain type of statistical distribution. Inevitably this attempt at unification is largely a précis of Benoit Mandelbrot's researches.^{2,42,43,44,45,46,47}

This approach, besides thwarting wasted effort, has the advantage that it makes available statistical tools that are neutral towards rival explanations of this type of behaviour. Actually, as Fairthorne¹⁷ pointed out in 1958, it is non-conformity, rather than conformity with it, that needs explanation. It is difficult to defeat in situations where the objects or actions of interest are

FAIRTHORNE R A, 1969. Empirical hyperbolic distributions (Bradford-Zipf-Mandelbrot) for bibliometric description and prediction[J]. *Journal of Documentation*, 25(4) :319-343.

1972

1972: 科尔兄弟 (Cole & Cole) 反驳了奥尔特加假设, 该假设认为每一位科学家都对科学的进步有所贡献。他们声称, 主要是精英科学家对科学进步作出了贡献 (Cole et al., 1972)。

The Ortega Hypothesis

Citation analysis suggests that only a few scientists contribute to scientific progress.

Jonathan R. Cole and Stephen Cole

Most scientists are aware that science is a highly stratified institution. Power and resources are concentrated in the hands of a relatively small minority. For the past several years we have been studying the social stratification system of science (1-3). Most of our research has concentrated on the social processes through which individual scientists are evaluated, to discover why some scientists rise quickly to positions of eminence and others remain relatively obscure. Two conflicting theories explain

social mobility in science. According to one theory the stratification system of science operates on strictly universalistic criteria: the scientists who publish the most significant work receive the ample recognition they deserve; those not publishing significant work are ignored. According to the other theory, a small elite at a handful of universities and government-supported laboratories control the social institutions of science in such a way as to perpetuate their own ideas and as-

to Progress in Science

Whereas most of our previous research has dealt with the processes through which individuals find their level in the stratification system, in this article we analyze another problem. We present data evaluating the comparative contributions of the various scientific strata to scientific progress, indicating whether progress is built on the labor of all "social classes" or is primarily dependent on the work of an "elite." In the past, historians and philosophers of science have attributed much of the growth of science to the work of the average scientist, who, it is suggested, has paved the way with his "small" discoveries for the men of genius—the great discoverers. This hypothesis is asserted in many sources, but perhaps no more clearly than in the words of Jose Ortega y Gasset (4):

For it is necessary to insist upon this extraordinary but undeniable fact: experimental science has progressed thanks in great part to the work of men astoundingly mediocre, and even less than mediocre. That is to say, modern science, the root and symbol of our actual civil-

Table 3. Citation patterns found in papers cited in the 1965 *Physical Review*.

Citations to paper in the 1965 <i>Physical Review</i> (No.)	Citations in 1965 to the life's work of major authors* cited in the papers	
	Mean No.	No. of major authors
24-49	175	(174)
20-23	169	(88)
10-17†	158	(215)
5-9	149	(124)
3-4	85	(65)

* By major authors is meant all single authors and for collaborative papers the author whose life work has received the highest number of citations in the 1965 SCI. † No papers were cited 18 to 19 times in *Physical Review* in 1965.

Cole JR, Cole S, 1972. The Ortega Hypothesis: Citation analysis suggests that only a few scientists contribute to scientific progress.[J]. Science, 178(4059), 368375.

1973

1973: 美国国家科学委员会首次发布了《科学指标报告》（Science Indicators）。

1973: 《社会科学引文索引》（Social Science Citation Index）发布。

1973

1973: 美国学者亨瑞·斯莫尔（Henry Small, 1941-）和前苏联学者林娜·马沙科娃（Irina Marshakova, 1941—2019）分别独立提出了共被引分析 (Small, 1973; Marshakova, 1973).

Henry Small (1941-) is Chief Scientist and Director of Research Service Group at Thomson ISI. He is one of the foremost scholars in the area of developing and applying co-citation analysis. This important work has resulted in a better understanding of the structure, relationships, and evolution of the sciences. Henry Small received several Awards including the JASIS Best Paper Award in 1987, and in 1998, the Award of Merit from the American Society for Information Science & Technology (ASIST). He has been named the sixth President of ISSI for the period of four years in 2003.

MARSHAKOVA IV, 1973. System of document connections based on references[J]. Nauchno-Tekhnicheskaya Informatsiya Seriya 2-Informatsionnye Protsessy I Sistemy, (6):3-8.

SMALL H, 1973. Co-citation in the scientific literature: A new measure of the relationship between two documents[J]. Journal of the American Society for information Science, 24(4), 265-269.

1975

1975: 迈克尔·莫拉夫奇克（Michael J. Moravcsik, 1928-1989）和普万纳林甘·穆鲁格桑（Poovanalingam Murugesan）提出了一种引文分类方案（Moravcsik et al., 1975）。

Michael J. Moravcsik (1928-1989) was called “multi-dimensional scholar and hero of third world science: physicist, scientometrician, music critic, and ambassador of science.” (E. Garfield and H. Small). Till 1989 he was professor of theoretical physics at the University of Oregon in Eugene.

MORAVCSIK M J, MURUGESAN P, 1975. Some results on the function and quality of citations[J]. *Social Studies of Science*, 5(1): 86-92.

1975

1975: 第一届国际信息科学研究论坛（IRFIS）由特
拉姆·克劳德·布鲁克斯（Bertram Claude Brookes,
1910-1991）组织，在伦敦举办。

Bertram C. Brookes (1910-1991) taught Information Science at the University College London and later at City University London. He was a pioneer in information science and one of founders of informetrics. He was active in both philosophy of science and quantitative science studies.

1976

1976: 普赖斯（Derek John de Solla Price, 1922 - 1983）使用成功孕育成功或累积优势原则（基于西蒙的工作）对信息计量学定律进行了建模（Price, 1976）。

Derek John de Solla Price (22 January 1922 – 3 September 1983) was a British physicist, historian of science, and information scientist. He was known for his investigation of the Antikythera mechanism, an ancient Greek planetary computer, and for quantitative studies on scientific publications, which led to his being described as the "Herald of scientometrics".

PRICE D J D S, 1976. A general theory of bibliometric and other cumulative advantage processes[J]. Journal of the American Society for Information Science, 27(5):292-306.

1976

Garfield, E. Preface and Introduction to Journal Citation Reports - Vol. 9 of the SCI, 1975

SCIENCE CITATION INDEX®

1975 ANNUAL

An International Interdisciplinary Index
to the Literature of Science, Medicine, Agriculture, Technology,
and the Behavioral Sciences

Volume 9

Journal Citation Reports®

A Bibliometric Analysis of References
Processed for the 1974
Science Citation Index®

compiled and edited
by

Eugene Garfield

isi®

Institute for Scientific Information®

Philadelphia

1976: 《期刊引证报告》（Journal Citation Reports, 简称JCR）发布。

JOURNAL RANKING PACKAGE JOURNAL CITATION REPORTS SECTION 1 PAGE 1

JOURNALS IN ALPHABETICAL ORDER

JOURNAL TITLE	CITATIONS IN 1974 TO			SOURCE ITEMS IN			IMPACT FACTOR	CITATIONS IN 1974 TO 1974 ITEMS	SOURCE ITEMS IN 1974	IMMEDIACY INDEX	
	ALL YEARS	1973	1972 73+72	1973	1972 73+72	1973					
1 A GRAEFES A KLIN E O	647	72	52	124	90	78	168	0.738	24	123	0.195
2 A VAN LEEUW J MICROB	557	47	53	100	62	55	117	0.855	15	63	0.238
3 AAPG BULL	1639	151	203	354	145	158	303	1.168	29	161	0.180
4 ABRASIVE ENG	1	0	0	0	25	35	60	0.000	0	24	0.000
5 ACCOUNTS CHEM RES	2738	326	555	881	63	56	119	7.403	65	62	1.048
6 ACTA AGRON HUNG	43	6	2	8	54	60	114	0.070	1	93	0.011
7 ACTA ALLEGOL	334	40	44	84	33	39	72	1.167	9	40	0.225
8 ACTA ANAESTH SCAND	287	25	37	62	54	48	102	0.608	8	61	0.131
9 ACTA ANAT	1212	47	84	131	141	142	283	0.463	17	157	0.108
10 ACTA ASTRONAUTICA	10	0	0	0	40	89	129	0.000	3	94	0.032
11 ACTA BIOCHIM BIOPHYS	250	15	51	66	32	51	83	0.795	7	46	0.152
12 ACTA BIOCHIM POL	336	34	31	65	37	37	74	0.878	11	51	0.216
13 ACTA BIOL CRACOV BOT	48	2	5	7	13	19	32	0.219	1	15	0.067
14 ACTA BIOL CRACOV ZOO	66	5	2	7	27	23	50	0.140	1	18	0.056
15 ACTA BIOL HUNG	227	4	15	19	27	43	70	0.271	1	15	0.067
16 ACTA BIOL MED GER	922	112	189	301	216	228	444	0.678	50	223	0.224
17 ACTA BOT NEER	465	45	43	88	76	76	152	0.579	16	64	0.250
18 ACTA CHEM SCAND	8803	472	720	1192	549	595	1144	1.042	165	434	0.380
19 ACTA CHIM HUNG	904	98	97	195	197	236	433	0.450	29	152	0.191
20 ACTA CHIR HUNG	54	6	9	15	45	32	77	0.195	3	133	0.091
21 ACTA CHIR SCAND	1645	64	142	206	142	137	279	0.738	26	133	0.195
22 ACTA CIENT VENEZ	64	6	14	20	77	101	178	0.112	0	10	0.000
23 ACTA CRYSTALLOGR	7598	22	18	40	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
24 ACTA CRYSTALLOGR A	1793	241	275	516	141	235	376	1.372	73	166	0.440
25 ACTA CRYSTALLOGR B	4520	854	984	1838	630	753	1383	1.329	221	635	0.348
26 ACTA CYTOL	763	98	93	191	81	90	171	1.117	8	73	0.110
27 ACTA DERMAT-VENEREOL	840	96	122	218	120	84	204	1.069	27	96	0.281
28 ACTA DIABETOL LAT	281	12	44	56	46	11	57	0.982	3	39	0.077
29 ACTA ENDOCRINOL PAN	12	0	6	6	8	10	18	0.333	0	0	0
30 ACTA ENDOCRINOL COP	4909	708	675	1383	251	311	562	2.461	159	278	0.572
31 ACTA ENTOMOL BOHEMOS	79	15	23	38	51	42	93	0.409	7	44	0.159
32 ACTA GENET MED GEMEL	122	1	5	6	13	33	46	0.130	0	61	0.000
33 ACTA GERONTOL	17	11	3	14	25	19	44	0.318	0	0	0
34 ACTA HAEMATOL	953	54	111	145	88	100	188	0.878	14	93	0.172
35 ACTA PATO-GASTRO	25	25	25	25	69	69	69	0.418	66	66	0

<https://garfield.library.upenn.edu/papers/jcr1975introduction.pdf>

1976

Francis Narin, 1934-

1976: 加布里埃尔·平斯基 (Gabriel Pinski) 和 弗朗西斯·纳林 (Francis Narin, 1934-) 提出了一种引文影响度量方法, 这是谷歌PageRank的前身(Pinski et al., 1976)。

PINSKI G, NARIN F, 1976. Citation influence for journal aggregates of scientific publications: Theory, with application to the literature of physics[J]. Information Processing and Management, 12(5):297-312.

1977

1977: 奈杰尔·吉尔伯特 (G. Nigel Gilbert, 1950-; 英国社会学家, agent-based models先驱) 认为说服力 (persuasiveness) 是引用的主要原因 (Gilbert, 1977)。

Geoffrey Nigel Gilbert CBE FBCS FRSA FAcSS FREng (born 21 March 1950) is a British sociologist and a pioneer in the use of agent-based models in the social sciences. He is the founder and director of the Centre for Research in Social Simulation (University of Surrey), author of several books on computational social science, social simulation and social research and past editor of the Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation (JASSS), the leading journal in the field.

GILBERT GN, 1977. Referencing as persuasion[J]. Social Studies of Science, 7(1):113-122.

1977

1977：钱学森（Qian XueSen）在《人民日报》发表“现代科学技术”一文，在我国最早倡导“科学的科学”研究（钱学森，1977）。

钱学森（1911年12月11日—2009年10月31日），浙江仁和（今杭州市）人，生于上海，中国空气动力学家和系统科学家，工程控制论创始人之一，中国人民解放军特级文职干部、一级英雄模范，中国科学院院士和中国工程院院士。

钱学森, 1977. 现代科学技术[N]. 人民日报（1977-12-9）.

1978

1978: Scientometrics期刊创刊，首任主编由普赖斯（Derek de Solla Price）、多勃罗夫（Gennady Michailovich Dobrov）、加菲尔德（Eugene Garfield）和贝克（Beck MT）共同担任，并由匈牙利科学院布劳恩（Tibor Braun）担任执行编辑（Price, 1978）

Derek de Solla Price

Tibor Braun

PRICE D J D S, 1978. Editorial statements[J]. Scientometrics , 1:7–8.

1978

1978: 《人文学艺术引文索引》（Arts & Humanities Citation Index）上线。

Arts & Humanities
Citation Index

via WEB OF SCIENCE™

1979: 奥托·纳克（Nacke O）和布莱克特（Blackert L）等分别独立提出了“信息计量学（informetrics）（Nacke, 1979; Blackert, 1979）”。

Informetrie

Informetrics

信息计量学

Professor Dr. med. Otto Nacke (1915 - 2006)

Professor Dr. med. Otto Nacke leistete auf dem Gebiet der medizinisch-wissenschaftlichen Dokumentation Pionierarbeit. Auf Prof. Nacke geht der Begriff Informetrie zurück. Näheres zu seinem Lebenswerk sowie seiner Biografie findet sich in der Zeitschrift 'Information - Wissenschaft und Praxis' (IWP) 56(2005)4, 240.

NACKE O, 1979. Informetrie. Ein neuer Name für eine neue Disziplin[J]. Nachrichten für Dokumentation, 30(6), 219-226.
BLACKERT L, SIEGEL K, 1979. Ist in der wissenschaftlich-technischen Information Platz für die Informetrie[J].
Wissenschaftliche Zeitschrift der Technischen Hochschule Ilmenau. 25(6):187-99.

1979

Michel Callon

1979: 米歇尔·卡隆 (Michel Callon, 1945-) 等提出了共词分析方法 (Callon et al., 1979)。

Michel Callon (born 1945) is a professor of sociology at the École des mines de Paris and member of the Centre de sociologie de l'innovation. He is an author in the field of Science and Technology Studies and one of the leading proponents of actor-network theory (ANT) with Bruno Latour.

CALLON M, COURTIAL JP, TURNER WA, 1979. L'Action Concertée Chimie Macromoléculaire: Sociologique d'une Agence de Traduction. Centre Sociologie de l'Innovation Paris/Strasbourg, Groupe d'Étude sur la Recherche Scientifique Université Louis Pasteur.

CALLON M, COURTIAL J, PENAN H, 1993. La scientométrie[M]. Paris: Presses Universitaires de France.

CALLON M, COURTIAL JP, TURNER WA, et al. 1983. From translations to problematic networks: An introduction to co-word analysis[J]. Social science information, 22(2) : 191-235.

1982

1982: 邱均平教授在武汉大学油印了《文献计量学》一书，该书一度成为科学计量学领域的重要学习资料。

1983-1984

1983：科学计量学领域的最高奖——德瑞克·约翰·德索拉·普赖斯纪念奖设立（The Derek de Solla Price Memorial Award），简称普赖斯奖。

1984：加菲尔德（Eugene Eli Garfield，1925 - 2017）博士获得了第一届普赖斯奖（The Derek de Solla Price Memorial Award）。

1985

1985: 赵红州 (Zhao Hongzhou, 1941 -1997) 出版了《科学能力学引论》，这是我国第一部科学计量学理论的集大成之作。

科学能力学引论

赵红州 著

科学出版社

内 容 简 介

本书是理论科学学的专门著作，主要讨论科学发展的内在动力问题。著者从系统论观点出发，讨论社会的科学能力诸要素及其相互作用所产生的新质，对科学家社会集团、图书情报系统、实验技术系统、劳动结构系统，以及科学教育系统的社会功能分别做了详细的分析，并用定量分析与定性分析相结合的方法，说明近代科学中心的转移问题、世界科学的未来问题和我国科学现代化的战略和战术问题。

本书既可供科技工作者和科学学专业工作者参考，又可供研究生、大学生和广大干部阅读。

科学能力学引论

赵红州 著

责任编辑 余志华

科学出版社出版

北京朝阳门内大街137号

中国科学院印刷厂印刷

新华书店北京发行所发行 各地新华书店经售

1984年12月第一版 开本：850×1168 1/32
1984年12月第一次印刷 印张：21 3/4 插页：3
印数：0001—8,000 字数：303,000

统一书号：17051·281

本社书号：3774·17-2

定价：3.55元

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• ii •

1985

Terrence Alan Brooks

1985: 特伦斯·布鲁克斯 (Terrence Alan Brooks, 爱荷华大学) 首次对引用者动机 (citer motivations) 进行了研究 (Brooks, 1985)。

BROOKS TA, 1985. Private acts and public objects: An investigation of citer motivations[J]. Journal of the American Society for Information Science, 36(4) : 223-229.

1985

1985/1990: 利欧·埃格赫（Leo Egghe, 1952-）正式证明了文献计量学法则的数学等价性（Egghe, 1985; Egghe, 1990; Egghe, 2005）。

Leo Egghe (1952-)

EGGHE L, 1985. Consequences of Lotka's law for the law of Bradford[J]. Journal of Documentation, 41(3), 173-189.

EGGHE L, 1990. The duality of informetric systems with applications to the empirical laws[J]. Journal of Information Science, 16(1), 1727.

EGGHE L, 2005. Power laws in the information production process: Lotkaian informetrics[M]. Emerald Group Publishing Limited.

1987

1987: 利欧·埃格赫 (Leo Egghe, 1952-) 在比利时迪彭贝克组织了第一届国际文献计量学和信息计量学会议 (1st International Conference on Bibliometrics and Theoretical Aspects of Information Retrieval, 后来被称为ISSI会议)。

Leo Egghe (1952-)

1988

1988：第一届科学与技术指标会议（Science & Technology Indicators Conference, STI）在荷兰莱顿召开。

1988

1988：安东尼·范瑞安（Anthony F.J. van Raan, 1945-）主持主编的《量化科学技术元勘手册》（Handbook of quantitative studies of science and technology）出版（van Raan, 1988）。

VAN RAAN AFJ, 1988. Handbook of quantitative studies of science and technology[M]. Elsevier.

1989

1989: 莱顿大学科学技术元勘中心（Centrum voor Wetenschaps- en Technologiestedies, 即 CWTS）成立，安东尼·范瑞安（Anthony F.J. van Raan, 1945-）担任首任主任。现任主任为卢多·瓦特曼（Ludo Waltman）。

Prof. dr. Ton van Rann
莱顿大学CWTS 的创始人和第一届主任（1989—2010年）。

Prof. dr. Paul Wouters
社会与行为科学学院院长。2010-2018年担任CWTS 中心主任。

Prof. dr. Sarah de Rijcke
科学与评估研究教授兼
CWTS 主任（2018-2023）。

Prof. dr. Ludo Waltman
科学定量研究教授
兼CWTS 主任（2023-至今）。

1989

1989：中国科学院图书馆中国科学引文索引数据库（Chinese Science Citation Database，简称CSCD）上线。

中国科学院文献情报中心

National Science Library, Chinese Academy of Sciences

CSCD 中国科学引文数据库

1992

1992：中国科学学与科技政策研究会科学计量学与信息计量学专业委员会成立，蒋国华担任第一届主任委员。

1993

1993: 我国科学计量学先驱赵红州 (Zhao HZ) 先生获得国际普赖斯奖提名 (首位被提名的中国人), 当年获奖者为匈牙利科学院学者舒伯特。

1993: 国际科学计量学与信息计量学学会 (International Society for Scientometrics and Informetrics, 简称ISSI) 成立, 克雷奇默 (Hildrun Kretschmer, 1947-) 担任第一届主席。

1995

(Henry Etzkowitz, 1940—) (Loet Leydesdorff, 1948-2023)

1995：亨利·埃茨科威兹（Henry Etzkowitz, 1940—）和路特·莱兹多夫（Loet Leydesdorff, 1948-2023）提出了“三螺旋（Triple Helix）”这一术语，用于研究大学-政府-产业之间的协同关系（Etzkowitz et al., 1995）。

ETZKOWITZ H, LEYDESDORFF L, 1995. The Triple Helix-University-industry-government relations: A laboratory for knowledge based economic development[J]. EASST review, 14(1) :14-19.

1995

1995: 国际科学计量学与信息计量学学会创办会刊JISSI: International Journal of Scientometrics and Informetrics(Discontinued), 首任主编由克雷奇默 (Hildrun Kretschmer) 担任。

Hildrun Kretschmer
(1947-)

1997

1997: 托马斯·阿尔明德（Tomas Almind）和彼得·英格森（Peter Ingwersen, 1947-）提出了“web(o) metrics（网络计量学）”（Almind et al., 1997）。

Peter ingwersen was born 1947 and became Student (mathematics/physics) 1965 from St. Jørgens Gymnasium, Frederiksberg, Staff Sergeant, Gardehusar Regiment, Næstved, 1966-68. Graduated as Librarian from the Royal School of LIS (RSLIS), Copenhagen, Denmark, 1973. Ph.D. , Copenhagen Business School, 1991.

ALMIND T C, INGWERSEN P, 1997. Informetric analyses on the world wide web: methodological approaches to 'webometrics'[J]. Journal of documentation, 53(4):404-426.

1998

Sergey Mikhailovich Brin (Russian: Сергей Михайлович Брин; born August 21, 1973) is an American businessman and computer scientist who co-founded Google with Larry Page.

Lawrence Edward Page (born March 26, 1973) is an American businessman, computer scientist, and internet entrepreneur best known for co-founding [Google](#) with [Sergey Brin](#).

1998: 谢尔盖·米哈伊洛维奇·布林 (Sergey Mikhaylovich Brin, 1973-) 和拉里·佩奇 (Lawrence Page, 1973-) 提出了PageRank算法 (Brin et al., 1998)。同年, 他们共同创立了谷歌公司 (Google)

BRIN S, PAGE L, 1998. The anatomy of a large-scale hypertextual web search engine[J]. Computer Networks and ISDN Systems, 30(1-7) :107-117.

1998

1998：南京大学中文社会科学引文索引数据库（Chinese Social Sciences Citation Index，简称CSSCI）上线。

1999

Albert-László Barabási

1999: 阿尔伯特-拉斯洛·巴拉巴西 (Albert-László Barabási, 1967-) 和瑞卡·阿尔伯特 (Reka Albert, 1972-) 引入了“优先连接” (preferential attachment) 这一术语, 用来描述被称为“累积优势”、“成功孕育成功”或“尤尔过程 (Yule process)” 的现象。

Michalis Faloutsos

1999: 米哈利斯·法洛索斯 (Michalis Faloutsos) 等发表论文《关于互联网拓扑的幂律关系》 (On Power-Law Relationships of the Internet Topology) 证明了互联网上的链接遵循幂律分布 (Faloutsos et al., 1999)。

FALOUTSOS M, FALOUTSOS P, FALOUTSOS C, 1999. On power-law relationships of the internet topology[J]. ACM SIGCOMM computer communication review, 29(4) :251-262.

2002

2002: 史蒂文·莫里斯 (Steven Morris, 俄克拉荷马州立大学) 开发了科技文献数据库信息可视化与分析系统, 即 Database Information Visualization and Analysis System, 简称DIVA (Morris et al., 2002)。

Figure 49. DIVA main GUI.

Figure 2. Research front timeline for the anthrax case study.

MORRIS S, DEYONG C, WU Z, et al, 2002. DIVA: a visualization system for exploring document databases for technology forecasting[J]. Computers & industrial engineering, 43(4):841-862.

2003

2003: 陈超美教授 (Chaomei Chen, 1960—; 美国德雷塞尔大学教授) 开发了科学知识图谱工具CiteSpace。

Chaomei Chen, 1960-

2004

2004: 加菲尔德博士 (Eugene Eli Garfield, 1925—2017) 团队开发了HistCite科学计量分析工具。

Eugene Eli Garfield (September 16, 1925 – February 26, 2017) was an American linguist and businessman, one of the founders of bibliometrics and scientometrics. He helped to create Current Contents, Science Citation Index (SCI), Journal Citation Reports, and Index Chemicus, among others, and founded the magazine The Scientist.

2004

2004： 安东尼·范瑞安（Anthony F.J. van Raan, 1945-）提出了睡美人文献（Van Raan, 2004）。

Anthony (Ton) van Raan studied mathematics, physics and astronomy at the University of Utrecht (with 1999 Nobel Laureate Martin Veltman as one of his theoretical physics teachers) and graduated (M.Sc.) in 1969. In 1973 he received a PhD in physics at the University of Utrecht, with a thesis on the interaction between electrons and helium atoms.

VAN RAAN AFJ, 2004. Sleeping beauties in science[J]. Scientometrics, 59(3):467-472.

2004

2004: 爱思唯尔 (Elsevier) 上线了Scopus。

2004: 谷歌学术 (Google Scholar) 上线。

2005

2005: 凯文·博亚克 (Kevin Boyack, 1962-) 等首次在期刊层面制作了全球科学地图 (Boyack et al., 2005)。

Kevin W. Boyack (USA) (1962-) received his PhD in Chemical Engineering at Brigham Young University in 1990. After studying combustion processes at Sandia National Laboratories, he became involved in a project where a new visualization technique developed at Sandia (VxInsight/VxOrd) was used to create highly detailed maps of the ISI databases used to aid Sandia's internal funding allocation and collaboration activities.

BOYACK K, KLAVANS R, BORNER K, 2005. Mapping the backbone of science[J]. Scientometrics, 64(3) :351-374.

2005

2005: 乔治·赫希 (Jorge Hirsch, 1953-; 物理学家) 提出了h指数 (Hirsch, 2005).

Jorge Eduardo Hirsch (born 1953) is an Argentine American professor of physics at the University of California, San Diego. Hirsch received a PhD in physics from the University of Chicago in 1980 and completed his postdoctoral research at the Kavli Institute for Theoretical Physics at the University of California, Santa Barbara in 1983. He is known for inventing the h-index in 2005, an index for quantifying a scientist's publication productivity and the basis of several scholar indices.

HIRSCH JE, 2005. An index to quantify an individual's scientific research output[J]. Proceedings of the National academy of Sciences, 102(46):16569-16572.

2005

2005: 汤森路透（Thomson Reuters, 现为科睿唯安）上线了“世纪科学（Century of Science）”数据库，使其引文索引数据库可以回溯到1900年。

2006

Leo Egghe (1952-)

2006: 利欧·埃格赫 (Leo Egghe, 1952-) 提出了 g-index (Egghe, 2006) 。

$$g = \left(\frac{\alpha - 1}{\alpha - 2} \right)^{\frac{\alpha - 1}{\alpha}} T^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}$$

Leo Egghe (1952-) is Professor and Chief Librarian at Hasselt University (Belgium).

EGGHE L, 2006. Theory and practise of the g-index[J]. Scientometrics, 69(1) :131-152.

2006

2006: COLLNET创办会刊 Journal of Scientometrics and Information Management, 并由Hildrun Kretschmer担任主编。

Hildrun Kretschmer
(1947-)

2007

2007: 爱思唯尔（Elsevier）创建了《信息计量学报》（Journal of Informetrics）并由 Leo Egghe担任主编。

Leo Egghe (1952-)

2008

2008: 文森特·丹尼尔·布隆代尔（Vincent Daniel Blondel, 1965）提出了社区发现的鲁汶算法 (Blondel et al., 2008)。

Vincent Daniel Blondel (born April 28, 1965) is a Belgian professor of applied mathematics and former rector of the University of Louvain (UCLouvain) and a visiting professor at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT). Blondel's research lies in the area of mathematical control theory and theoretical computer science. He is mostly known for his contributions in computational complexity in control, multi-agent coordination and complex networks.

BLONDEL VD, GUILLAUME JL, LAMBIOTTE R, LEFEBVRE E, 2008. Fast unfolding of communities in large networks[J]. Journal of Statistical Mechanics: Theory and Experiment, 10: P10008.

2009

Nees Jan van Eck

Ludo Waltman

2009: 莱顿大学CWTS尼斯·杨·凡·艾克（Nees Jan van Eck, 1982—）和卢多·瓦特曼（Ludo Waltman, 1982-）开发了VOSviewer软件。

2009

2009: 奥利·佩尔松 (Olle Persson, 1949-) 开发了BibExcel科学计量工具。

Olle Persson (1949-) is Professor emeritus in Library and Information Science and was the founder of the Inforsk research group at Umeå University (Sweden) where he teaches Library & Information science. He developed the toolbox BibExcel which is broadly used by the bibliometric community.

2010

Jason Priem

2010: 杰森·普里姆（Jason Priem）等发布了《替代计量学宣言》（Altmetrics manifesto）（Priem et al., 2010）。

altmetrics

PRIEM J, TARABORELLI D, GROTH P, et al, 2010. Altmetrics: A manifesto. <https://altmetrics.org/manifesto/>.

2011

2011: 尤安·艾迪 (Euan Adie) 等研发的Altmetric数据库上线。

Euan Adie

Altmetric

2021

2021：中国科学学与科技政策研究会科学计量学与信息计量学专业委员会会刊Data Science and Informetrics创办，首任主编由邱均平教授担任。

2012

2012: 美国旧金山举办的美国细胞生物学学会年会上，一线科学家与一些学术期刊的编辑和出版商会商后，针对影响因子（JIF）滥用等学术评价问题发布了《旧金山宣言》（San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment）（DORA, 2012）。

DORA, 2012. San Francisco declaration on research assessment. <http://www.ascb.org/dora/>.

2015

Diana Hicks

Paul Wouters

COMMENT

SUSTAINABILITY Data needed to drive UN development goals **p.432**

CONSERVATION Economics and environmental catastrophe **p.434**

GEOLOGY Questions raised over proposed Anthropocene dates **p.436**

HISTORY Music inspired Newton to add more colours to the rainbow **p.438**

The Leiden Manifesto for research metrics

Use these ten principles to guide research evaluation, urge **Diana Hicks**, **Paul Wouters** and colleagues.

Data are increasingly used to govern science. Research evaluations that were once bespoke and performed by peers are now routine and reliant on metrics. The problem is that evaluation is now led by the data rather than by judgement. Metrics have proliferated: usually well intentioned, not always well informed, often ill applied. We risk damaging the system with the very tools designed to improve it, as evaluation is increasingly implemented by organizations without knowledge of, or advice on, good practice and interpretation.

Before 2000, there was the Science Citation Index on CD-ROM from the Institute for Scientific Information (ISI), used by experts for specialist analyses. In 2002, Thomson Reuters launched an integrated web platform, making the Web of Science database widely accessible. Competing citation indices were created: Elsevier's Scopus (released in 2004) and Google Scholar (beta version released in 2004). Web-based tools to easily compare institutional research productivity and impact were introduced, such as InCites (using the Web of Science) and SciVal (using Scopus) as well as software to analyse individual citation profiles using Google Scholar (Publish or Perish, released in 2007).

In 2005, Jorge Hirsch, a physicist at the University of California, San Diego, proposed the *h*-index, popularizing citation counting for individual researchers. Interest in the journal impact factor grew steadily after 1995 (see 'Impact-factor obsession'). Lately, metrics related to social usage

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2015: 美国佐治亚理工学院的公共政策教授Diana Hicks等在荷兰莱顿召开的国际会议上，提出了合理利用科学评价指标的七条原则,后来发展成为《莱顿宣言》（Leiden Manifesto）(Hicks et al., 2015)。

HICKS D, WOUTERS P, WALTMAN L, et al, 2015. the Leiden Manifesto for research metrics[J]. Nature, 520(7548):429-431.

2015

James Wilsdon

2015: 詹姆斯·威尔斯登（James Wilsdon）等发布了《计量潮》研究报告（Metric Tide: Report of the Independent Review of the Role of Metrics in Research Assessment and Management, Wilsdon et al., 2015）。

WILSDON J, ALLEN L, BELFIORE E, et al, 2015. The metric tide. Report of the independent review of the role of metrics in research assessment and management.

2015

CP
CHANDOS
PUBLISHING

Becoming Metric-Wise

A Bibliometric Guide
for Researchers

Ronald Rousseau, Leo Egghe, Raf Guns

2015: 鲁索·桑德拉（Rousseau Sandra）和罗纳德·鲁索（Ronald Rousseau, 1949—）提出了“计量智慧”（metric-wiseness）这一术语（Rousseau et al., 2015）。

Rousseau Sandra

Ronald Rousseau

ROUSSEAU S, ROUSSEAU R, 2015. Metric-wiseness[J]. Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology, 66(11):2389-2389.

2016

Chaomei Chen, 1960-

2016: *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics* 创刊，结合metrics 和 analytics，并呼吁在计量的同时，更加应该注重“分析”。首任主编为美国德雷塞尔大学陈超美教授。

2017

2017: I40C上线。

I40C

2018 2018: 《科学学》（Science of Science）综述长文在Science杂志发表，标志着科学学的研究进入了新时期（Fortunato et al., 2018）。

FORTUNATO S, BERGSTROM C T, BÖRNER K, et al, 2018. Science of science. Science, 359(6379) : eaao185.

2018

2018: Dimensions数据库上线。

2018: Journal of Altmetrics创刊，主编由Judit Bar-Ilan担任。

2019

Ludo Waltman

2019：国际科学计量学与信息计量学会（International Society for Scientometrics and Informetrics）创建了会刊《量化科学元勘》（Quantitative Science Studies），由麻省理工大学出版社出版。首任主编为卢多·瓦特曼（Ludo Waltman）。

Quantitative Science Studies

2019

2019: 尤安·艾迪 (Euan Adie) 等研发的政策引文数据库Overton上线 (Szomszor et al., 2022)。

Euan Adie

SEARCH POLICY DOCUMENTS SEARCH PEOPLE SEARCH SCHOLARLY ARTICLES

Search **14,242,018** policy documents

e.g. universal credit Search policy

We'll search the titles and full text of the policy documents we index. You can use booleans (AND, OR, NOT), "phrases in quotes", the ~ operator and a number after phrases to allow word gaps, and parentheses. See our help page on advanced searches for more.

Example searches:

"Tobacco packaging" *covid-19 AND masks* *title:"World Development Report"* *"Phillips Curve Netherlands"~40*

SZOMSZOR M, ADIE E, 2022. Overton: A bibliometric database of policy document citations[J]. Quantitative science studies, 3(3):624-650.

2019

2019：文森特·特拉格（Vincent Traag）、卢多·瓦特曼（Ludo Waltman）和尼斯·杨·凡·艾克（Nees Jan van Eck）提出了莱顿算法（Traag et al., 2019）。

Vincent Traag

Ludo Waltman

Nees Jan van Eck

TRAAG VA, WALTMAN L, VAN ECK NJ. 2019. From Louvain to Leiden: guaranteeing well-connected communities[J]. Scientific reports, 9(1):5233.

2022

Jason Priem

2022: 杰森·普里姆（Jason Priem）等研发了大型开放科学文献数据库OpenAlex: The open catalog to the global research system上线（Priem et al., 2022）。

PRIEM J, PIWOWAR H, ORR R, 2022. OpenAlex: A fully-open index of scholarly works, authors, venues, institutions, and concepts. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2205.01833>.

2022

2022：杭州电子科技大学《邱均平颜金莲教育发展基金》和 Data Science and Informetrics编辑部共同发起设立了“邱均平计量学奖”。该奖项是国内首个科学计量学领域的专门奖项。

邱均平教授

2022

Samuel Harris Altman (born April 22, 1985) is an American entrepreneur and investor best known as the CEO of OpenAI since 2019 (he was briefly fired and reinstated in November 2023). He is also the chairman of clean energy companies Oklo Inc. and Helion Energy.

2022-2023: 科学研究迎来新范式——AI for Science, 颠覆性AIGC产品ChatGPT问世, AI从此开始将深刻影响科学学的研究。

ChatGPT

2023-2024

2024: 大型中文科学计量学工具书《科学计量学手册》（Handbook of Scientometrics）出版（李杰等，2024b），共有250余名国内外学者参加，17位普赖斯奖获得者为《手册》撰写了给年轻一代的寄语，中文序言（蒋国华教授），英文序言（Ronald R）。

李杰，张琳，黄颖等，2024. 科学计量学手册[M]. 北京：首都经济贸易大学出版社.

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Handbook of Scientometrics

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陈悦 胡志刚 杨思洛 副主编

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丛书主编: 李杰

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